

Color Contrast Samples

Foreground
#FFFFFF
RGB(255,255,255)

Background
#002D62
RGB(0,45,98)

Ratio
13.53

#000000
RGB(0,0,0)

#FFFB00
RGB(255,251,0)

19.05

#000000
RGB(0,0,0)

#FFFFFF
RGB(255,255,255)

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